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SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF UZBEK NATIONAL ART OF EMBROIDERY

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Abstract : The article describes the modern development directions of embroidery based on the study of the unique features of the Uzbek national embroidery art. The directions of modern development of embroidery have been determined based on research with students studying design.

Key words: Embroidery, pattern, tools, floral decorations, needle, needle, national values, practical art.

Introduction. Embroidery - needle on | decorative art or craft. The art of fabric or other materials yarn through is a | embroidery has developed over the

centuries and has been widely used to decorate fabrics. The origins of embroidery date back to the Modern Man period or 30,000 BC. During a recent archaeological survey, fossilized remains of hand-stitched and decorated clothing, boots, and headdresses were found [1].

The art of sewing related to embroidery and many other types of fabric decoration has been proven by the results of many archeological studies. The development of primitive humanity realized that the stitches used to join animal skins could also be used for decoration. Historical monuments, statues, paintings and vases depicted by the population on various ancient objects depict people wearing thread-embroidered clothes.

At the stage of historical development of embroidery, small pearls were widely used to decorate religious items. With that together The business of sewing beads on clothes has also developed. By 1500 BC, embroidery was developing in Central Asia as well as in other regions of the world. It is in the Uzbek national embroidery art that in the 1700s, thread and bead embroidery became popular. At the same time as human clothing, embroidery began to be used to decorate home furnishings and many other items.

Uzbek national embroidery is considered one of the most ancient types of folk craft art, and it was formed as a result of the goal of the nation to make its life beautiful. The art of embroidery has been used to decorate national clothes and household items since ancient times.

Today, our national embroidery art is gaining fame not only in our country, but also in foreign countries due to its unique beauty and rich patterns. Uzbek people's hand-embroidered kirkip, sozana, zardevor, flower quilt, bedclothes etc. United States of America, France, Italy, Japan, Germany, Belgium, America, India and Russian Federation is seen as a permanent exponent of high importance in art museums of countries such as

In the sources and miniatures of the XIV-XV centuries, we can find embroidery samples on a large scale. For example, the Spanish ambassador Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo, who lived in the palace of Amir Temur, wrote in his memoirs that he watched the embroidery decorations in the palace. Behzod also depicted an embroidered tent in the miniature "Temur on the Throne" (1467), which he worked on for the "Zafarnama" manuscript.

The diversity of embroidery stitches, embroidery, and styles testifies to the great art of Uzbek embroiderers. For example, in Nurota, Bukhara, Samarkand, embroidery products are sewn with a more wide stitch, in Shahrisabz, with a wide stitch, kandakhayol, Iraqi, and in Tashkent, with a printed stitch. The changes in social life affected the traditions of embroidery and the types of products [2].

In the course of our research, the antiquity of our national embroidery was conducted using the available evidence of archaeological findings and written sources in the territory of the Central Asian countries. Based on the analysis of the historical sources on embroidery, it can be noted that it is through the miniatures of the XIV-XV centuries that we can note the unique development of embroidery. The invention of the embroidery machine in the 19th century led to an increase in the number and variety of new watches in the industry. In addition, it became possible to implement embroidery colors and types of patterns in high symmetrical sizes. Despite this, the tradition of hand-stitching many types of embroidery has been preserved among our people, and a large-scale craft style is developing to this day [3].

Since ancient times, the way of life, culture and rituals of the peoples of Central Asia have been very close to each other. In particular, in Tajik embroidery, beautiful flowers, circular, flower branches, nightingale, circular patterns are used a lot, while in Uzbek embroidery, plant-like, geometric and floral patterns are reflected more. Geometric, plant-like forms, flowers,

birds and fruits are often depicted in Russian embroidery. Kazakh and Kyrgyz embroidery are closer to each other, in which, in addition to flowers, geometric shapes, more animals, horn and hoof-like elements are depicted in different colors.

According to the ancient traditions of the peoples of Central Asia, including the Tajik people, embroidered items were given to Tajik girls as a dowry when they were given in marriage. The bridal dress of the bride is also decorated with beautiful patterns, such as her headscarf, veil, dress, skirt, and even her shoes. In the house of the bride, the bed, the fabric (rojjo) thrown over the blanket, rice, carpet, supra and other household items are decorated with the same pattern as above. The horse and cart carrying the bride to the house where the bride is transferred are also made in the same way [4].

The most amazing thing is that the brides-to-be had to prepare all kinds of embroidery for these dowries themselves. On the day of the wedding, they judged how beautiful the bride was by looking at the things hung in the groom's house. Therefore, girls were taught to embroider from the age of 7-9. After three or four years, they started to embroider independently. Chevar embroiderers tried to express their dreams of beauty according to their art and nature. The finer and more beautiful the embroideries are, the more expensive they are.

Embroidery is one of the ancient branches of applied art. Archeological findings show that embroidery is ancient in almost all nations, and that it has developed under the influence of climate, natural conditions, and the culture, art, and professions of each nation. The appearance of embroidery is connected with the appearance of seams and stitches in leather clothes. During periods, it is connected with the transition from stones, bones, beads, metal beads, weaving, as well as fabric weaving, dyeing and other works [5,6].

Nowadays, the rich and unique artistic wealth and national values of our people, as well as the material and spiritual life of the Uzbek people, have become the basis for the development of modern culture in our country and abroad. The importance of the chosen topic is that in the art of embroidery, which has developed since ancient times in Uzbekistan, we can see in the following pictures that the secrets of the craft have been perfectly mastered and this craft has been raised to the level of art.

The introduction of Islamic culture to Central Asia at the beginning of the 8th century caused the further development of art of decoration and painting. Live creatures in majestic paintings were replaced by images of nature, patterns with plant-like and geometric elements. Arabic writing was assimilated and the decorative (epigraphic) style appeared. In painting, the symbolic philosophical meanings of various shapes, floral elements and colors began to be expressed more widely:

- ✓ Square - eternity, stability.
- ✓ The sun is a symbol of life.
- ✓ Zirk flower (gulsafsar) peace and longevity.
- ✓ Apple is a symbol of love.
- ✓ The lion is a symbol of courage, justice and strength.
- ✓ Humo is a bird that brings happiness.
- ✓ Green is mother earth.
- ✓ The color of the air is clear sky.

The above-mentioned forms of embroidery have started to be expressed in various modern forms while maintaining their importance even today. Then, the opinions of design students regarding the reflection of the above-mentioned shapes and colors in modern Uzbek national embroidery were studied by means of a questionnaire. In the survey, the opinions of 212 students studying in the field were studied. According to the results of the survey, it was emphasized that there is a need to express such shapes as the square, Sun, zirk flower, apple, lion and

huma bird as elements of embroidery and that they are important in connecting with our historical traditions.

In the use of colors in embroidery, it was emphasized that along with the results

of modern color science, green and orange should be kept as central colors. Samples of works of art named "Our national embroidery in your imagination" by our students are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. A sample of our national embroidery

Based on the analysis of embroidery images created by students, it should be noted that while preserving our ancient traditions, it is necessary to pay special attention to modern colors and types of patterns. Formation of embroidery art samples based on today's market economy and marketing requirements is of urgent importance.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that in the art of embroidery, each nation has its own patterns that are used the most, and it is important to develop them based on the requirements of the time. It is necessary for students studying in the field of visual arts to develop their knowledge and skills related to the art of embroidery in accordance with the traditions and values of the Uzbek nation.

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